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Erasmus+ Project

lightcode

Strengthening the Digital
Transformation of Higher Education
Through Low-Code

The LightCode Manifesto

Analysis of the survey through questionnaires
and focus groups in partner countries

University of
Macedonia
& all partners

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INTRODUCTION

In the age of rapid technological advancements and the ever-increasing demand for digital solutions, the LightCode project emerged as a beacon of innovation and collaboration. The LightCode project, a collaborative effort involving partners from five countries (France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, Austria), has embarked on a mission to explore the potential of low-code application development in the field of higher education. This project seeks to address the growing demand for more efficient and accessible digital solutions within educational institutions.

In this document, we present an analysis of the questionnaires administered to faculty members, students, and stakeholders across partner countries. These surveys sought to gauge their familiarity with low-code development, identify potential challenges, and assess the perceived benefits of integrating low-code solutions into the educational domain. Additionally, focus group discussions with faculty members provided valuable qualitative insights into their perspectives and expectations. All the data gathered from these sources have been meticulously analyzed to draw meaningful conclusions. The following sections will delve into the detailed findings and insights gathered from these different groups of participants. Through an in-depth exploration of their responses, we aim to draw valuable conclusions that will inform the future direction of the LightCode project.

Consequently, "The LightCode Manifesto" is a testament to our collective efforts and insights, distilled from a comprehensive analysis of the data we gathered. Our journey has uncovered intriguing trends and valuable lessons, as well as opportunities and challenges that lie ahead. In this manifesto, we present our findings, general conclusions, and recommendations that transcend geographical boundaries and underscore the universal importance of low-code application development. However, this document is not a mere recounting of our shared experiences; it is a clarion call to action, a master

plan for the future, and a declaration of our unwavering commitment to empower individuals and organizations with the requisite knowledge and tools to thrive in an increasingly digitalized world.

FACULTY MEMBERS' FINDINGS - QUESTIONNAIRES

1. Description of the participants

116 faculty members participated in the survey through questionnaires across the partner countries. These questionnaire results paint a diverse picture of faculty members across the surveyed countries, encompassing a broad spectrum of age groups, genders, and academic disciplines. The description of the most important demographic characteristics of the participants follows.

In France, 33 faculty members completed the questionnaires. The majority of the participants (48%) were in the age category of 51 or more, followed by 36% in the 41-50 age range. Only 12% of the participants were aged 31-40, and a very small fraction (3%) were between 26-30 years old. In terms of gender distribution, 61% of the participants are male, while 39% are female. When asked if they have experienced any form of discrimination or exclusion in their lives based on factors such as gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and disability, 58% of the respondents answered "No" to experiencing any form of discrimination or exclusion throughout their lives. On the other hand, 39% answered "Yes", and 3% preferred not to say. This suggests that a significant portion of the faculty members in France did not perceive themselves as having encountered such issues, though a notable fraction have experienced some form of discrimination or exclusion.

In Greece, the questionnaire garnered responses from 32 faculty members, offering valuable insights into their demographics and experiences. Notably, a significant portion (66%) of the participants fell within the age bracket of 41-50 years, reflecting a mature and experienced cohort. The sample was predominantly male (75%) and all participants held PhD degrees. A noteworthy finding was that the majority of respondents (90,6%) reported no personal experiences of discrimination or exclusion based on factors such as gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, or disability. However, a few participants

(9,4%) did acknowledge facing discrimination, with gender-related issues being the most commonly cited form. The diversity of academic backgrounds among the respondents was striking, spanning various departments and institutions. Disciplines ranged from Computer Science and Business Administration to Psychology and Civil Engineering. This diversity underscores the potential for cross-disciplinary collaboration and highlights the varied expertise of the faculty members, who hailed from renowned institutions like the National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, the University of Macedonia, the Athens University of Economics and Business, and the Hellenic Open University.

In Croatia, the survey encompassed 21 faculty members affiliated with the Faculty of Economics & Business in the University of Zagreb. The sample distribution showed that the majority of respondents (71.43%) fell into the 31-40 age group, reflecting a relatively young academic cohort. Gender-wise, the sample was skewed towards males, constituting approximately two-thirds of the respondents. It was noteworthy that a significant portion (71.43%) reported never experiencing exclusion throughout their lives, while the remainder (23.81%) had encountered exclusion, with two respondents attributing it to gender-related factors. The educational background of the respondents was predominantly characterized by PhD degrees, with a few holding master's degrees. This suggests a strong academic foundation among the participants, despite varying levels of familiarity with low-code concepts.

In Serbia, 17 faculty members took part in the survey, providing insights into their demographic characteristics and experiences. The age distribution indicated that nearly half (47%) of the participants were in the 31-40 age category, with an almost equal distribution of genders (53% male and 47% female). The respondents' academic qualifications exhibited a mix of PhD holders and those in the process of obtaining their PhDs, showcasing diverse stages of academic progression. When asked about experiences of discrimination or exclusion, almost half of the respondents denied any such

encounters, while 7 participants acknowledged experiencing various forms of discrimination, primarily related to economic barriers. 2 individuals reported discrimination related to biopsychosocial issues. The faculty members came from diverse academic backgrounds, with a predominant presence in engineering sciences, especially electrical, technical, and mechanical engineering, underscoring the importance of fostering interdisciplinary cooperation and involving social sciences faculty members more extensively.

Austria's survey involved 13 faculty members from various universities and higher education institutions. The participants exhibited a wide age range, with the majority (38.5%) being 51 years and older, while a significant portion (30.8%) was relatively young, falling in the 26-30 age group. The gender distribution showed a slight male majority (61.5%). Encouragingly, only 23.1% of respondents reported experiencing exclusion throughout their lives, with the primary reason being perceived gender-based preferences in project assignments. The respondents represented diverse academic departments, including Electrical Engineering, Medicine, Law, and Architecture, showcasing the cross-disciplinary nature of faculty members' expertise and highlighting the potential for collaboration and knowledge exchange.

2. Familiarity with the low-code development approach

The survey responses across all countries revealed varying levels of awareness and understanding of low-code application development among faculty members. In France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria, participants were asked whether they had heard of the term "low-code development". In France, out of the 33 faculty members who participated, 14 (around 42%) have heard of the term "low-code application development", while 19 (around 58%) have not. In Greece, approximately 56% of respondents had heard of it, while 44% had not. In Croatia, about two-thirds of the sample were familiar with the concept, while one-third was not. Serbia's responses were relatively balanced,

with 47% having heard of the term and 53% not familiar with it. Austria had the lowest level of awareness, with 69.2% of participants reporting that they had never heard of low-code development.

Among those who were familiar with low-code development, the survey results demonstrated a reasonably good understanding of the concept. Respondents described low-code development as a method that simplifies software development, often utilizing visual tools like drag-and-drop interfaces, reducing the need for extensive programming skills. These descriptions suggest that faculty members generally comprehended the core concepts of low-code.

The survey results showed limited formal training in low-code approaches across all countries. In France, a significant majority, about 88% (29 out of 33), reported not having received any formal training in low-code approaches. Only 12% (4 out of 33) had undergone such training. This highlights a gap in formal education on low-code technologies among the faculty. In Greece, 29 out of 32 participants (90.6%) reported that they had not received any formal training in low-code methods. Croatia also had a predominantly negative trend, with none of the respondents providing specific details about training they may have undergone. Serbia had only two out of 17 respondents (11.8%) reporting formal training in low-code approaches, and again, no specific training details were provided. Austria had a similar trend, with 84.6% of participants reporting that they had never received training in low-code approaches. The limited exposure to formal training may be indicative of the current state of familiarity with low-code development within these academic communities.

Responses regarding whether faculty members had unknowingly used low-code environments were mixed across the surveyed countries. In France, about 39% acknowledged using low-code platforms, while nearly 36% denied any such experience. This inconsistency could indicate a lack of clear understanding or awareness about low-code platforms among some faculty members. In Greece, 50% responded affirmatively, and 31% initially answered negatively but later

contradicted themselves in subsequent responses, suggesting a lack of clarity or awareness regarding low-code environments. Croatia also had 85.71% of respondents believing they might have used a low-code platform without realizing it. Serbia had nearly 60% of respondents expressing a similar belief. Austria showed that 69.2% of respondents believed they might have used a low-code environment without realizing it. These findings highlight potential instances of encountering low-code tools without full awareness, emphasizing the importance of education and awareness campaigns to ensure that faculty members can fully leverage low-code environments.

The survey revealed a diverse range of low-code platforms and tools that faculty members across all countries have used at least once. These platforms included WordPress, Joomla, Google Apps, PowerApps, and more. WordPress emerged as the most commonly used platform, suggesting its prevalence in various academic applications. This diversity in experiences indicates that faculty members have engaged with low-code approaches for various purposes, including website development and application creation.

Teaching experiences related to low-code approaches were relatively limited across all countries. Specific details regarding the integration of low-code methods into teaching practices were not provided for France. While some faculty members in Greece, Croatia, and Serbia mentioned integrating low-code methods into their teaching, the overall prevalence of such teaching was low. Applications of low-code teaching included entrepreneurship courses, workflow automation, system integration, data analysis, and machine learning, indicating the versatility of low-code approaches in academia. In Austria, none of the participants reported having taught low-coding techniques, suggesting that the integration of low-code methods into teaching practices remains niche within Austrian higher education.

3. Advantages & Disadvantages of the low-code development approach

Across all surveyed countries (France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria), faculty members were asked to assess the importance of statements related to the advantages of the low-code development approach. The responses provide valuable insights into their perceptions of the benefits of low-code development.

In France, faculty members' perceptions of the advantages and disadvantages of low-code development reveal a nuanced understanding of its impact in academic settings. When assessing the advantages, the faculty rated "Lower Barrier to Entry, Deployment Cost, and Time" with an average score of 3.36, highlighting the economic and temporal efficiencies that low-code platforms can offer. This aspect is particularly relevant in academic environments where resources are often limited and there's a need for quick prototyping in student projects. "Improved Agility" received a high rating of 3.12, indicating that the flexibility provided by low-code platforms is valued, especially in research settings where requirements often change rapidly. However, "It Changes Easily" received a lower average rating of 2.27, suggesting concerns about the stability or robustness of low-code solutions for long-term academic projects. "Higher Productivity Across Teams" was rated at 3.0, reflecting an awareness of the collaborative benefits of low-code platforms, which is crucial given the interdisciplinary nature of academic research.

The faculty members in Greece, on average, rated the advantages of low-code development at 3.6, indicating a moderate to high level of importance. They highly valued aspects such as "Lower barrier to entry, deployment cost, and time", "Rapid assembly of solutions by a non-technical audience", and "Democratization of software development". These elements received particularly high average ratings, all above 3.7, reflecting the importance placed on accessibility and efficiency in low-code development. However,

"Better customer experience" received a relatively lower average rating of 2.8, suggesting that it might be perceived as less critical in the context of low-code development.

The respondents in Croatia perceived "rapid assembly to a non-technical audience," "higher productivity," and "lower barrier to entry" as the most prominent advantages of the low-code development approach. These factors were rated highly by participants. However, their assessments generated reasonably heterogeneous answers, indicating that while some advantages were widely recognized, there was diversity in opinions regarding the importance of specific benefits.

Faculty members in Serbia placed the highest importance on the fact that low-code developed applications can easily change and that they decrease costs. They gave lower importance to the idea that low-code contributes to the democratization of software development. This suggests that faculty members recognize the potential for flexibility and cost reduction through low-code approaches but may not view it as a transformative force in software development democratization.

In Austria, 46.2% of participants considered "Lower barrier to entry, deployment cost, and time" and "Rapid assembly of solutions by a non-technical audience" as very important advantages of low-code development. Other advantages such as "Improved agility", "Decreased costs", "Speeding up development cycles", and "Automating any business idea in minutes" were also considered important. However, "Democratization of software development" and "Better customer experience" were viewed as less important. This suggests that Austrian faculty members emphasize the practical and cost-related benefits of low-code approaches.

Faculty members were also asked to assess the importance of statements related to the disadvantages of low-code development, providing insights into their concerns about potential drawbacks.

In France, on the disadvantages side, "Can't Be Applied to More Complex Processes" emerged as a significant concern with the highest average rating of 3.0. This indicates that faculty members foresee limitations in utilizing low-code platforms for complex computational tasks, which are common in research projects. "Security Risks" also raised substantial concern, with an average rating of 3.03, revealing the importance of data security in academic contexts. These concerns suggest that while faculty members in France recognize the value of low-code development in fostering economic and operational efficiencies, they are also wary of its limitations, particularly in terms of handling complex tasks and ensuring security. This balanced perspective could be instrumental in shaping institutional policies or curricula related to software development.

On average, faculty members in Greece rated the disadvantages of low-code development at 3.4, indicating a moderate level of concern. The statement "Can't be applied to more complex processes" received the highest average rating of 3.9, indicating that respondents saw limitations in the applicability of low-code development to complex scenarios. Concerns about "Skipping checks and balances during production" and "Security risks" were also notable, with average ratings of 3.5 and 3.6, respectively. This suggests that faculty members in Greece have reservations regarding the complexity and security aspects of low-code development.

The respondents in Croatia expressed a notable concern about security risks, the impossibility of applying low-code to more complex processes, and limitations as the main disadvantages of the low-code approach. These aspects generated the largest weight in their assessments. However, their responses showed reasonable heterogeneity, indicating diverse opinions regarding the importance of specific disadvantages.

Faculty members in Serbia rated "security risks" as the most important disadvantage of low-code development, followed by concerns about limitations.

They placed relatively lower importance on the need for a basic understanding of the programming world. This suggests that security is a primary concern, while the need for programming knowledge is seen as less critical.

In Austria, "Security risks" and "Low-code development platforms have limitations" were considered the most important disadvantages of the low-code development approach. "A basic understanding of the programming world is required" and "Less ability to add custom code" were also viewed as important drawbacks. However, some participants were unsure about whether "No ownership of the source code" and "Skipping checks and balances during production" were important disadvantages. This suggests that faculty members in Austria have significant concerns about security, limitations, and the need for programming knowledge.

4. The low-code development approach & Higher Education

In France, majority (64%) of the respondents have not used low-code in their careers, and 45% of them have never heard of it, indicating limited exposure and awareness of low-code approaches among the faculty. This indicates that low-code approaches are not yet widespread among the surveyed faculty members in France, which could reflect a gap in exposure or training in this area.

The responses from faculty members in Greece regarding their use of the low-code approach in their careers reveal a mix of experiences. About 37% of respondents have used low-code methods, while 44% have not. Additionally, 19% are unsure or do not know about their use of low-code. This suggests a varied level of familiarity and adoption of low-code development approaches within the Greek academic community. While some faculty members have embraced low-code approaches in their careers, others may not have encountered or explored this approach extensively. This diversity of

experiences reflects the varied backgrounds and expertise levels within the faculty.

In Croatia, roughly two-thirds of respondents have never used low-code applications in their careers, indicating a relatively low level of adoption among faculty members. This suggests that there is significant untapped potential for introducing low-code approaches in educational settings to enhance productivity and collaboration.

In Serbia, only 24% of respondents have used the low-code approach in their careers, while 70% have not. This indicates that there is a need for substantial improvement in faculty members' professional skills and knowledge regarding low-code environments. The gap in knowledge and skills is even more pronounced among faculty members in social sciences, indicating a potential opportunity for cross-disciplinary training and collaboration.

In Austria, 61.5% of the participants have never used low-code application development approaches in their careers, and 7.7% are unsure about it. This suggests that low-code adoption among faculty members in Austria is relatively low. The responses reflect a cautious or skeptical approach to low-code development, with some participants expressing uncertainty about its benefits.

When participants were asked about the difficulties encountered in using low-code, several points were highlighted. Firstly, in France, the significant number (45%) of faculty members who have never heard of low-code suggests a gap in knowledge and educational initiatives. This lack of awareness suggests that there is room for educational initiatives to increase familiarity with low-code development approaches.

In Greece a significant portion (31%) had never heard of low-code, indicating a lack of awareness or exposure to this approach. Furthermore, 25% had heard of low-code but hadn't received any training, suggesting a potential gap in knowledge and skills development. Some faculty members (28%) mentioned

that they know how to utilize low-code's potential but find it not applicable to their work, indicating that the suitability of low-code solutions varies depending on the specific tasks or projects. Lastly, 16% highlighted the cost aspect, stating that while they understand low-code, the subscription fees for low-code application development platforms are perceived as relatively high. These findings demonstrate that there is a need for greater awareness, training, and cost-effective solutions to promote the adoption of low-code in academia.

Faculty members in Croatia faced difficulties primarily related to a lack of awareness or training in low-code development. Some respondents had never heard of it, while others had heard of it but hadn't received training. These challenges point to the need for educational initiatives and training programs to introduce low-code to faculty members and build their skills.

In Serbia, the majority of respondents had heard of low-code but had not received training, indicating a knowledge gap that needs to be addressed. Additionally, some faculty members mentioned that they knew how to use low-code but found it inapplicable to their work, suggesting that the suitability of low-code solutions should be carefully assessed for specific tasks or projects. The cost aspect was also highlighted as a concern, emphasizing the need for cost-effective solutions to promote low-code adoption.

In Austria, the participants' responses reflected challenges related to a lack of awareness and training in low-code development. Some participants mentioned that they had never heard of low-code, while others were unsure about its benefits. This underscores the importance of raising awareness and providing training opportunities for faculty members to enhance their understanding and use of low-code.

Regarding the expectations and benefits of low-code development approach, the responses of faculty members in France quite varied, but "No idea" appeared three times, indicating some level of uncertainty or lack of knowledge about what low-code can offer. This diverse set of responses reflects the

different perspectives faculty members have, likely based on their unique experiences and fields of expertise.

However, in Greece they believe that low-code development can offer them benefits such as speed, ease of use, cost-effectiveness, and the ability to rapidly develop solutions for everyday tasks. They also see value in low-code for creating proof-of-concept projects, automating workflows, and improving communication with students. However, some respondents were not familiar with low-code and its potential benefits.

Respondents in Croatia anticipated benefits from low-code, such as better reach to individuals without programming skills, easier communication among interdisciplinary team members, flexibility, and cost savings. These expectations align with the practical advantages of low-code development. Faculty members in Serbia expressed expectations that low-code can offer rapid development of applications, easier maintenance of course websites, improved communication with students, and the ability to bring programming closer to students with limited prior experience. These expectations reflect a recognition of low-code's potential in simplifying tasks, enhancing communication, and expanding educational opportunities. In Austria, participants believed that low-code development could offer them the ability to develop required software more easily, without relying on experts. Some participants emphasized the potential for quick and cost-effective solutions, while others expressed concerns about the limitations of low-code platforms. These expectations suggest a cautious approach to low-code adoption, with an emphasis on practical benefits.

Responses about the potential benefits of using the low-code development approach to teaching revealed a positive atmosphere. In France, the responses show a wide range of opinions on the benefits of low-code, indicating multiple potential applications in academic settings. The unique and diverse views

suggest that there could be specific, yet unexplored, applications of low-code beneficial for academic outcomes.

Faculty members in Greece recognized the potential benefits of integrating low-code application development into tertiary education. These benefits include introducing students to design principles, prototyping, problem-solving skills, and bridging the digital literacy gap. Low-code was seen as a practical way for students to develop complete, useful applications quickly, aiding in teaching complex concepts and enhancing communication with students.

Respondents in Croatia identified potential benefits of low-code in teaching, such as bridging the gap between different professions, enabling better understanding of interdisciplinary collaborations, and providing hands-on experience for students to bring their ideas to life. They also saw potential in using low-code for lab exercises in business and management education.

Faculty members in Serbia saw potential benefits in using low-code for teaching, including rapid development of applications and websites, easier interaction between professors and students, problem-solving before concrete understanding of programming techniques, and improving communication with students. Low-code was also seen as a means to bring programming closer to students with limited prior experience.

In Austria, participants recognized the potential benefits of low-code in teaching, including better training of students, enhanced two-sided communication with students, and the opportunity to develop proof-of-concept projects for lectures. However, some participants expressed concerns about the need for students to have a basic understanding of programming concepts to fully benefit from low-code.

5. Familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer"

In France, the overwhelming majority of faculty members (32 out of 33) indicate that they have not heard of the term "Citizen Developer". This lack of

familiarity is rather striking, especially considering that these are faculty members in fields that are increasingly influenced by technology. It raises questions about how current their curriculum might be and whether it includes emerging roles and trends in the software development ecosystem.

The responses from faculty members in Greece regarding their familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer" reveal a mixed level of awareness. While some respondents (5 out of 32) have heard of the term, a majority either indicated that they have not (23 out of 32) or responded with "I don't know" (4 out of 32). This suggests that the concept of Citizen Developers, individuals who create software or applications without formal coding backgrounds, may not be widely recognized or understood within the surveyed faculty. This indicates a need for education and awareness-building efforts, particularly within academic circles, to ensure that faculty members and students are well-informed about emerging technological trends like Citizen Development.

In Croatia, respondents are mostly unfamiliar with the term "Citizen Developer," suggesting a low level of awareness. Their responses when asked to explain the term also varied widely, reflecting different interpretations. This diversity in interpretations indicates that there may not be a universally established definition of Citizen Developer, and its meaning can vary based on context and perspective.

In Serbia, respondents showed a surprisingly low level of familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer," with only one positive response. The provided explanations of the term show a range of understandings, such as individuals creating simple applications independently, anyone being able to program without extensive IT knowledge, and the use of out-of-the-box tools for application design.

In Austria, the majority of participants (84.6%) had never heard of the term "Citizen Developer". Some participants attempted to guess the meaning, with responses ranging from non-programmers creating software to individuals

without formal programming skills using low-code solutions. These answers indicate a lack of familiarity with the term within the surveyed group.

Responses regarding whether the business world uses Low-Code approaches are mixed. In France, the most common response to the adoption of low-code in the business world was "I don't know", given by 10 out of 33 respondents. This suggests a marked level of uncertainty or lack of information among faculty about current business practices in software development. In Greece, some participants (14 out of 32) strongly believe that the business world employs Low-Code approaches, while others are more hesitant and respond with "maybe" (10 out of 32) or "I don't know" (7 out of 32). This diversity in responses suggests a level of ambiguity and possibly limited awareness about the extent to which Low-Code approaches are utilized in the business sector. The presence of "maybe" responses implies that some participants may have heard about low-code but are unsure about its widespread adoption. In Croatia, faculty members largely believe that the business community uses low-code approaches, as indicated by their responses. This aligns with the perception of low-code as a practical solution for application development in various industries. In Serbia, a significant majority of respondents (76.5%) are aware of the use of low-code in the business world. This indicates a relatively high level of awareness among faculty members about the adoption of low-code approaches in business processes. In Austria, a majority of participants (61.5%) believe that the business world uses low-code approaches, suggesting a moderate level of awareness. However, it's worth noting that nearly 40% of participants indicated that they understand there is a growing need for Citizen Developers, indicating that they recognize the changing landscape of software development.

Responses regarding the increasing need for Citizen Developers show also a range of opinions. Again in France, the most frequent response regarding the growing need for Citizen Developers is "I don't know," provided by 18 out of 33 faculty members. This uncertainty reflects the broader lack of familiarity

with the concept of Citizen Developers and their significance in the modern business and technology landscapes. In Greece, while some participants firmly believe that there is a growing demand for Citizen Developers (14 out of 32), others are less certain and respond with "maybe" (10 out of 32). Interestingly, a few participants explicitly state that they do not know (7 out of 32) or have enough information to form an opinion on this matter. This diversity of responses may stem from differences in participants' awareness of the role and significance of Citizen Developers in application and software development. In Croatia, faculty members generally seem to agree on the need for Citizen Developers, as indicated by their responses. The positive perceptions align with the idea that Citizen Developers can bridge the gap between technical and non-technical roles in organizations. In Serbia, half of the respondents believe that there is a growing need for Citizen Developers, while others are uncertain or do not have enough information to form an opinion. This suggests that while some faculty members recognize the evolving role of Citizen Developers, there is still a degree of uncertainty or lack of awareness about their increasing importance. In Austria, the participants largely understand that there is a growing need for Citizen Developers. This recognition aligns with the changing dynamics of application development, where individuals with diverse skill sets can contribute to the creation of software solutions.

6. Low-code approach & the business world

In France, the faculty members have varied opinions on the benefits of low-code approaches for businesses. Interestingly, the most frequent response was "I don't know", which suggests a lack of familiarity or perhaps scepticism about the utility of low-code platforms in a business setting. However, among those who did offer an opinion, the benefits cited align well with the general advantages associated with low-code development—namely, speed, agility, and cost-effectiveness. These attributes are particularly valued in businesses

that aim to be nimble and responsive to market changes. The varied responses also touch upon the democratisation of software development, allowing employees without formal coding experience to participate in application development. This has implications for organisational efficiency and innovation.

In Greece, faculty members perceive various advantages of using low-code approaches for businesses. They highlight the speed and agility that low-code platforms offer, enabling quick problem-solving, idea validation, and process automation. The ease of creating applications, even for non-developers, is seen as a significant benefit, potentially leading to a greater number of applications and innovative solutions. Cost reduction is another key advantage, attributed to the use of less specialized personnel, increased employee knowledge about application development, and improved competitiveness in the digital transformation landscape. Overall, these responses emphasize that low-code can enhance business efficiency, innovation, and cost-effectiveness while involving a broader range of individuals in application development processes.

In Croatia, faculty members primarily emphasize lower costs and increased agility as the main benefits of low-code for businesses. This aligns with the idea that low-code platforms can streamline development processes and reduce the need for extensive coding expertise.

In Serbia, there is a general awareness of the potential benefits of low-code for businesses. Respondents mention advantages such as easy content creation, easier maintenance, increased productivity and creativity through better teamwork, shorter development times, and lower development costs. They highlight the democratizing aspect of low-code, enabling anyone to create applications useful for their company's needs. While most respondents are aware of the benefits, it's clear that not all have concrete low-code application ideas to implement.

In Austria, participants see several advantages of low-code for businesses, with a strong emphasis on cost reduction. They note that lower costs can result from not having to hire external experts and from allowing employees to develop applications without extensive coding knowledge. The potential for increased productivity and efficiency is also mentioned, along with the ability to create custom-tailored applications quickly. Participants also express concerns about the need for foolproof solutions due to the risk associated with users' lack of technical knowledge.

Regarding application suggestion, a significant number of respondents indicated that they do not have an idea for developing an application using low-code approaches, suggesting either a lack of familiarity with what low-code platforms can achieve or perhaps a focus on more traditional, code-intensive development methods. For those who did have ideas, their suggestions were quite diverse, ranging from business process automation to educational tools. This diversity reflects the versatility of low-code platforms to address a wide array of challenges across different sectors. In Greece, while responses regarding potential low-code application ideas vary, some participants mention ideas such as data processing and dashboard creation, managing operational processes, appointment scheduling systems, e-commerce platforms, psychometric test creation, and educational materials for teaching Python. These ideas demonstrate a range of potential use cases for low-code development, from data management and education to e-commerce and utility applications like parking space locators. However, not all participants have concrete low-code application ideas at this time. In Croatia, respondents did not provide specific low-code application ideas that they themselves could build. This suggests that while they may recognize the benefits of low-code, they may not have identified specific projects or applications for its implementation. In Serbia, some respondents have concrete low-code application ideas, such as web pages for promoting scientific content, service-finding applications, and teaching platforms. However, it's evident that only a few participants have specific low-code application ideas ready for

development. In Austria, participants describe various low-code application ideas that they believe could be built using low-code approaches. These ideas include marketing apps, automation solutions, teaching platforms, online shops, and architectural geometry preparation for use in virtual reality systems. These responses showcase a range of potential applications across different domains, emphasizing the versatility of low-code development.

It's worth noting that the faculty members who could envision applications for low-code platforms are not just recognizing the capabilities of these tools, but they are also implicitly acknowledging the shifting landscape of software development. Their ideas are a nod to the democratisation of application development, where you no longer need to be a seasoned programmer to bring an application from concept to reality. Overall, the responses to these questions underscore the need for more education and awareness among faculty about emerging trends in software development, particularly as they have significant implications for both industry practices and academic curricula.

7. Training on Low-code approach

In France regarding the interest in low code training the responses indicate a mixed level of interest among faculty members when it comes to receiving training on low-code capabilities and uses. A plurality of respondents (13 out of 33) expressed interest ("Yes"), highlighting a proactive stance toward acquiring new skills and knowledge in this emerging field. However, the remainder of the respondents were either not interested or unsure. This suggests that while there is a segment of the academic community that is eager to engage with new technological trends like low-code platforms, there is also a significant portion that may require more information or persuasion to recognize its value.

In Greece, faculty members' interest in receiving training related to low-code development approaches is diverse. While a significant portion expresses interest in such training (19 out of 32), a sizable group declines the offer (10 out of 32), and a few remain uncertain (3 out of 32). This range of responses suggests that faculty members' interest in low-code training is not uniform. Some may already possess knowledge or skills in this area, while others may not see a direct need for such training in their roles. The diversity of responses underscores the importance of tailoring training programs to meet individual needs and levels of expertise when implementing low-code solutions in educational settings. In Croatia, the majority of respondents express interest in receiving low-code training, indicating a willingness to explore and learn about this technology. In Serbia, nearly half of the respondents express interest in participating in low-code training programs, while others are either not interested or unsure. This diversity in responses emphasizes the need to customize training programs to cater to the specific needs and preferences of faculty members. In Austria, a relatively lower percentage of participants express interest in receiving online training on low-code capabilities and uses. A significant proportion responds with "maybe," indicating that their interest may depend on the attractiveness and potential benefits of the training program.

Regarding preferred training methods, in France, among those who expressed interest in training, the preferred modes were highly individualised, ranging from online courses to in-person sessions. This diverse range of preferences underscores the need for flexible training solutions that can cater to various learning styles and schedules. Faculty members in Greece have diverse preferences. Some participants prefer online and asynchronous education, appreciating the flexibility of self-paced learning and online community engagement. Others favour in-person training, and a few suggest a combination of online and offline methods. The use of online platforms, open-source tools, tutorials, and webinars is also mentioned. However, a small number of respondents are unsure about their preferred training methods,

possibly indicating a need for guidance in selecting suitable options. In Croatia, respondents predominantly highlight workshops as their preferred training platform. Workshops offer interactive learning experiences and may facilitate hands-on practice with low-code tools. Faculty members in Serbia express preferences for various training methods, including live or online courses, workshops, and training sessions that focus on creating specific projects. This diversity suggests that a range of training formats should be considered to accommodate different learning styles. In Austria, specific preferences for training methods are not detailed in the provided information. However, the responses from other countries emphasize the importance of offering diverse training options to cater to the varied needs and preferences of faculty members.

FACULTY MEMBERS' FINDINGS - FOCUS GROUPS

1. Description of the participants

40 faculty members participated in the survey through focus groups across the partner countries. More specifically, in France, 2 focus groups were conducted, one with 5 participants (4 men and 1 woman) and the other with 6 participants (3 men and 3 women). In the first focus group, all participants had PhD degrees, and they were faculty members from computer science or related departments, specifically from Paris-Dauphine University. They are involved in teaching subjects such as programming, software development, data analysis, and more, given their specializations, at both undergrad and graduate levels. The second group had participants from various faculties, including Liberal Studies, Drawing/Photography/Communication, Sociology, Entrepreneurship, Business, Economics, and Management. Among them, 5 had PhD degrees and 1 had a Master's degree.

In Greece, 2 focus groups were conducted, one with 5 participants (3 men and 2 women) and the other with 6 participants (3 men and 3 women). The first group comprises faculty members from diverse departments, including computer science, business administration, and social sciences. They cover a wide range of subjects related to their disciplines, including programming, management, and data analysis, among others. Faculty members teach across various academic years, from undergraduate to postgraduate levels, depending on their departments and programs. Similar to the first focus group, participants in the second group come from diverse faculties, including engineering, humanities, education, and natural sciences. These faculty members teach at the undergraduate level. The inclusion of participants from different faculties and teaching areas highlights the potential applicability and relevance of low-code approaches across a wide range of academic disciplines and fields of study.

The focus group in Croatia included 8 participants, with an equal distribution of male and female participants. The majority of participants were in the 31-40 age group, followed by a smaller number in the 26-30 age group and one participant in the 41-50 age group. All participants in this focus group work at the Faculty of Economics & Business. They teach various courses across different academic years, covering subjects such as international business, statistics, economic theory, marketing, finance, and informatics.

The focus group in Serbia consisted of 6 female faculty members from the Faculty of Economics, representing different academic positions, including Full Professors, Associate Professors, Teaching Assistants, and an officer for international relations. These faculty members are involved in teaching various disciplines and subjects, including Economics, Statistics, Law, Corporate Governance, and Financial and Managerial Accounting. They teach across all levels of studies, including bachelor, master, and doctoral programs, in both large and small groups.

In Austria, 4 faculty members participated in the focus group interview. The discussion primarily focused on the aspect of exclusion and discrimination within universities and institutions. While one participant didn't observe gender discrimination in his department due to the low number of women, others had different impressions. They noted that it can be more challenging for women to advance in their careers, which is reflected in the lower number of female professors.

2. Familiarity with the low-code development approach

In France, regarding the computer science group, when it comes to familiarity with the concept of "low-code application development," the majority of the participants in the first group, which consists of faculty members in Computer Science, are well-acquainted with the term. Specifically, 4 out of 5 have heard

of it. The participants hold varied viewpoints on what the term encompasses, including perspectives that see it as a way to build applications with minimal coding skills and simple interfaces for code generation. Despite this familiarity with the concept, it is noteworthy that none of the participants have received formal training on low-code approaches and techniques. This could suggest a gap in institutional training programs, especially considering that these are Computer Science faculty members who are otherwise technically proficient. In the Non-Computer Science focus group, familiarity with "low-code application development" is somewhat mixed. Three out of the six participants have heard of the term. Responses regarding what the term includes were diverse, ranging from those who think it's about not having to code in the traditional way to those who admittedly have no idea. Interestingly, one participant in this group has received training on low-code approaches, suggesting that interest in or exposure to low-code development is not strictly limited to technically-oriented disciplines.

In Greece, two focus groups provided insights into how participants perceive the concept of "low-code application development method". The first group, comprising individuals from various faculties, including computer science and business administration, described it as a modern approach to software development that doesn't demand extensive coding skills. They highlighted its capacity to simplify application creation through visual tools and pre-built components, making the development process more accessible and efficient. However, two participants specializing in social sciences lacked knowledge and practical experience in this domain. Surprisingly, none of the members in this group reported teaching low-code approaches in their courses. The second group in Greece, consisting of participants from diverse faculties, associated low-code with an approach that streamlines application development by minimizing the need for extensive coding. These participants, including those from non-technical backgrounds, perceived low-code as a way to create applications efficiently through visual interfaces and pre-built components. However, those from non-technical backgrounds had limited exposure to low-

code training, while participants from technical departments had practical experience with low-code tools and services. Similar to the first group, none of the members in this group reported teaching low coding approaches in their courses.

In Croatia, participants in focus groups showed diverse levels of familiarity with the term "low-code application development method." While most associated it with creating applications without requiring extensive programming knowledge or simplifying the programming process, some were unfamiliar with the term. Interestingly, one participant in Croatia mentioned using a low-code development platform to create a software application design environment through a graphical user interface.

In Serbia, faculty members from the social sciences exhibited varying levels of familiarity with low-code application development methods, primarily influenced by individual backgrounds and interests. While some had practical experience with low-code platforms, formal education in this area was often lacking. The integration of technology and low-code development into the curriculum was inconsistent, relying on personal interests and institutional support.

Austria's participants indicated that participants had used low-code applications without realizing it, with WordPress being a popular choice.

Regarding education and training in low-code development approach, in Greece, participants from the first focus group, particularly those from technical backgrounds, had received formal training or engaged in self-education regarding low-code techniques. However, the second group included participants from non-technical backgrounds who had limited exposure to low-code training. Despite these differences, neither group reported teaching low-code approaches in their courses.

In Croatia, the focus group findings indicated that only two out of eight participants had participated in some form of education or training on low-code approaches and techniques. These experiences often centered around specific tools or use cases. Additionally, a significant portion of participants in Croatia had never used a low-code development approach in their careers.

In Serbia, formal education in low-code application development was lacking among faculty members from the social sciences. While some engaged in workshops, online courses, or collaborations with colleagues from technical departments, low-code education depended largely on personal interests.

Austria's survey revealed that while the term "low-code" was new to participants, many had unknowingly used low-code applications. Specific training or education in low-code development was not extensively discussed in the Austrian context.

Regarding practical experience with low-code tools, in Greece, participants from the first group, particularly those from technical backgrounds, mentioned practical experience with various low-code platforms such as WordPress, Salesforce, Google Apps, and PowerApps. These tools played a substantial role in website development, automation, and application creation. However, participants from non-technical backgrounds in the second group had limited or no experience with low-code tools.

In Croatia, about half of the focus group participants reported never having used a low-code development approach in their careers. Those who had used low-code tools mentioned applications like Google applications, PowerApps, WordPress, Salesforce, Zoho, and Mendix. However, some participants expressed a lack of opportunity to use low-code applications in their careers.

Faculty members from the social sciences in Serbia had practical experience with low-code platforms like WordPress and Google Apps. However, this

experience varied depending on individual interests and the integration of technology into their research.

Austria's survey indicated that participants had used low-code applications, particularly WordPress, but the discussion on practical experience was limited.

Regarding the integration of low-code development approach in curriculum, in Greece, it appeared inconsistent across participants and faculties. Teaching low-coding techniques or methods was relatively rare among the participants, and only a few had opportunities to do so. Simultaneously, teaching low-coding approaches was mentioned by only one participant in Croatia, who taught in the field of information and communication sciences. This highlighted the limited integration of low-code education into the curriculum among Croatian focus group participants. In Serbia, the integration of low-code into the curriculum was inconsistent and depended on personal interests and institutional support. The Austrian focus group did not provide significant insights into the integration of low-code into the curriculum.

3. Advantages & Disadvantages of the low-code development approach

Regarding the advantages of the low-code development approach, in France, it is important to mention that nobody really uses low code platforms as teaching tools for their students. Some of them have personal experience in using no-code platforms. They admit their opinions are therefore based on presumptions and general information available on the web. Among the Computer Science faculty, there's a notable appreciation for the advantages of low-code development, particularly its ease of use and the rapid development it enables. They value how low-code platforms aim to simplify the software development process to make it more efficient.

Participants in Greece's focus groups recognized several advantages. In the first group, consisting of faculty members from various disciplines, these advantages included rapid development, cost savings, user-friendliness, agility, engagement, and simplification. The second group, which encompassed a mix of technical and non-technical backgrounds, highlighted the accessibility and innovation aspects of low-code. Both groups acknowledged the speed and cost-effectiveness of low-code, its potential for innovation in teaching and learning, and its applicability across diverse academic disciplines.

In Croatia, participants acknowledged the advantages of low-code development, including simplicity, reduced entry barriers, cost and time efficiency, and its potential to transform the corporate world. These advantages were seen as valuable, particularly for non-technical audiences who could easily assemble solutions.

In Serbia, faculty members in the social sciences viewed the low-code approach as versatile and accessible, empowering them to leverage technology for research, teaching, and administrative purposes. They highlighted the ease of use, user-friendly interfaces, fast development, cost-effectiveness, customization possibilities, and increased productivity associated with low-code platforms. Faculty members recognized its advantages in academic collaboration, research support, teaching improvement, and administrative efficiency.

Austrian participants emphasized the low barrier to entry and rapid assembly of solutions as significant advantages of the low-code approach. They also noted that it could lead to higher productivity by simplifying data analysis and structuring, aiding in decision-making. Some participants saw "no ownership of resource code" as an advantage, indicating open access.

Moving on to the disadvantages of the low-code development approach, the French focus groups acknowledge the limitations, notably the lack of customization options and challenges with scalability. The sentiment reflects a

nuanced understanding that low-code platforms, while beneficial, are not a universal solution for all software development needs. In the diverse non-Computer Science group, there's a more cautious optimism. Faculty members recognize the potential for cost savings and the user-friendliness of low-code platforms, but they don't seem as enthusiastic as their Computer Science counterparts. The limitations, such as restricted customization and scalability issues, are pointed out and seem to weigh more heavily on their overall perception. This could indicate that for fields less oriented toward software development, the limitations of low-code platforms are seen as more critical.

Participants in both focus groups from Greece expressed concerns about limited customization options, scalability challenges, dependency on platform providers, security, and a potential skills and learning gap, especially among students. These concerns revolved around issues related to control, scalability, reliance on third parties, data security, the depth of programming knowledge limited creativity, and the risk of overreliance on pre-built solutions. In Croatia, participants raised concerns about the limited application of the low-code approach in complex processes, security risks, and the perceived complexity of adding new features to low-code projects. Faculty members in Serbia's social sciences expressed concerns about the level of technical knowledge and skills required, limited control over data, maintenance requirements, and the need for ongoing platform updates. While recognizing its advantages, they highlighted potential limitations and challenges. Austrian participants noted concerns about security risks associated with low-code development.

4. The low-code development approach & Higher Education

In France, faculty members from both Computer Science and a variety of other academic disciplines recognize the significant benefits of integrating low-code development into higher education. From the perspective of Computer Science faculty, low-code is seen as a valuable asset for career advancement,

enhancing versatility in roles across academia and industry. They envision utilizing low-code platforms to make software development and application design courses more practical and engaging, while also acknowledging its potential for facilitating interdisciplinary collaboration. However, there's a noted scepticism among these educators about relying solely on low-code for learning coding, with a preference for a traditional, foundational approach.

Participants in Greece highlighted several potential benefits of implementing low-code development in higher education. These benefits, reflecting on the first focus group, include accessibility and inclusiveness by democratizing application development, rapid prototyping for faster results, interdisciplinary collaboration and real-world applicability, while reflecting on the second focus group, include reduced entry barriers, efficiency and time savings, and alignment with modern skills. All faculty members recognized that teaching students to use low-code platforms would prepare them for careers where rapid application development is essential.

In Croatia, participants noted that low-code development could benefit higher education by providing students with skills for future employment or entrepreneurial ventures. It could also improve student engagement, automate certain activities, encourage coding among faculty, and offer highly customizable solutions. Additionally, it could motivate both faculty and students to apply coding solutions to various course topics.

In Serbia, low-code development was seen as a versatile tool for higher education. It could streamline teaching processes, enhance student experiences, improve administrative efficiency, and enhance research capabilities, especially in data collection, processing, and analysis in economics and social sciences.

Austrian participants emphasized that learning minimal coding skills or low-code in university could give students a competitive edge in the job market. However, there were uncertainties about the direct impact on employability

and the extent to which low-code skills are valuable across all career areas. Participants also noted that curriculum updates and the willingness of professors to adapt play a crucial role in integrating low-code into higher education.

Regarding the low-code development approach's impact on their careers and training methods, in France, faculty members from diverse academic backgrounds appreciate low-code for different reasons. They recognize its potential in reducing entry barriers to application development, particularly for students with limited technical skills. This group believes that low-code platforms can lead to significant efficiency gains and time savings, especially in academic projects or research. Moreover, they see the teaching of low-code as aligning well with industry demands, preparing students for a job market that increasingly values practical application development skills.

In Greece, faculty members with technical backgrounds believed that proficiency in low-code development could positively impact their careers by making them more versatile educators and researchers. They envisioned incorporating low-code development into their teaching methods to make courses more practical and engaging. Low-code also offers expanded research opportunities and adaptability to student needs. In the second group, participants also saw career relevance, particularly in preparing students for the job market.

Croatian participants expressed mixed views on how application development through a low-code approach could impact their careers and teaching methods. Some saw it as a way to automate tasks, increase productivity, and offer customized solutions, while others were uncertain about its relevance to their work.

In Serbia, participants in the first focus group anticipated that low-code development would enhance their careers by making them more versatile and opening up opportunities in academia and industry. They planned to integrate

low-code into their teaching methods, enhancing practicality and relevance in courses. It also offered expanded research possibilities and adaptation to student preferences. In the second group, cross-disciplinary teaching, enhanced teaching strategies, career relevance, and meeting industry demands were recognized as potential benefits.

Austrian participants believed that learning low-code skills could be advantageous for students in the job market, but there were uncertainties about its universal applicability. They noted that curriculum updates and professor willingness were crucial for successful integration into teaching. Creating "low-code ambassadors" in universities was suggested to promote the low-code development approach.

5. "Citizen Developer" & the business world

In France, among the Computer Science faculty, the term "Citizen Developer" was generally well-understood. Faculty members in this group see a Citizen Developer as someone who is not a professional coder but can develop applications using low-code or no-code platforms. They believe that the business world is increasingly recognizing the value of Citizen Developers for their ability to quickly turn ideas into functional applications, thereby contributing to organizational agility and innovation. In contrast, the term "Citizen Developer" was less familiar among the Non-Computer Science faculty. Those who had heard of it had varying degrees of understanding but generally agreed that Citizen Developers could be valuable in a business context, especially in roles that require rapid application development.

Awareness of the term "Citizen Developer" among the faculty members in Greece varied. Those with technical backgrounds were more likely to be familiar with the term, understanding it as individuals who can create applications using low-code or no-code platforms. In contrast, awareness in

the second focus group was generally limited, with only a few participants having heard of it. Those familiar with the term had varying degrees of understanding. In Croatia, the majority of participants in the focus group were not familiar with the term "Citizen Developer." Most respondents associated it with individuals without formal programming education who still participate in application development. A few participants had different interpretations or were unsure about its meaning. In Serbia, faculty members in the focus group had limited understanding of the term "Citizen Developer" but were more familiar with concepts like organizational citizenship behaviour. They connected this IT terminology to their previous knowledge, gradually gaining a better understanding. Awareness of the term 'Citizen Developer' was generally low among Austrian focus group participants. They understood that having Citizen Developers in a company could enhance agility and productivity, but the concept was not well-established.

Considering the real-world exploitation of the low-code development approach, participants in Greece generally believed that the business world utilizes low-code approaches. They saw it as a means to achieve quicker and more efficient application development, aligning with businesses' goals of staying competitive and agile. Examples were provided in fields such as customer relationship management (CRM), e-commerce, project management, and workflow automation. In Croatia, focus group participants believed that the low-code approach is used in everyday business. Some were confident in this belief, while others had a more cautious perspective. In Serbia, faculty members were strongly aware of the potential of low-code approach implementation in the business community, public and NGO sectors, and other stakeholders. They recognized the cost reduction, faster time-to-market, improved customer experience, better communications, and higher productivity as potential benefits for businesses. Austrian participants had varying views on the use of low-code in the business world. Some believed that it was being employed, particularly in sectors where rapid application development is crucial. Others

were more skeptical or uncertain about its prevalence. The extent to which low-code is used might vary depending on the business's scale and nature.

Regarding Citizen Developers, in France, all the participants expressed a need for such individuals to work under the guidance of IT professionals to ensure the quality and security of applications. In Greece, participants in the first focus group generally agreed that there is a growing need for citizen developers. They cited increasing demand for digital solutions across industries and the role of citizen developers in bridging the gap between IT and business departments. However, in the second focus group, views were more varied. Some participants agreed that there is a growing need due to organizations' digitalization efforts, while others expressed concerns about the quality and security of applications created by citizen developers. In Croatia, some participants believed in the growing need for citizen developers, while others were more reserved or skeptical. They recognized the demand for citizen developers in the business world as organizations digitize their operations. In Serbia, participants were aware of the growing need for citizen developers, driven by the increasing demand for digital solutions in various industries. They acknowledged that citizen developers empower non-technical users within organizations and can reduce IT department backlogs. The need for citizen developers was not unanimous among Austrian participants. Some believed that being a citizen developer could be advantageous, especially within existing roles, but it may not be the defining skill for getting a new job. The concept of citizen developers was not yet well-established.

6. Training on Low-code approach

In France, computer Science faculty members were particularly enthusiastic about the potential of low-code. They see value in exploring low-code-based educational tools, like virtual labs or interactive quizzes, to enhance cross-disciplinary learning experiences. Faculty members from non-Computer Science

fields express interest in low-code training for somewhat different purposes. They envision developing applications for student services, including career guidance, internship matching, and mental health support, aiming to enhance the overall university experience for students. Additionally, they believe that low-code can be a valuable tool in pedagogical enhancement, helping to foster active learning, problem-solving, and creativity among students.

Regarding application ideas, in Greece, faculty members from the first focus group shared ideas related to educational tools, including interactive quizzes, virtual labs, collaborative study platforms, and academic management applications. These ideas aimed to enhance the learning experience, improve administrative processes, and support research activities. In the second focus group, ideas focused on student services, career guidance, internship matching, mental health support, language learning platforms, and research support applications. In Croatia, participants had limited ideas for developing low-code applications. Only one participant with a background in information and communication sciences suggested the development of simple business applications using a low-code approach. In Serbia, an innovative idea emerged during the focus group discussions—the creation of a "Faculty Feedback Tracker" application. This application could streamline the feedback collection process from students, providing valuable insights for faculty members and educational institutions. It would serve to enhance the overall quality of education and simplify administrative tasks associated with feedback management. Austria mentioned the possibility of establishing an extra-curricular course or integrating low-code development into existing IT classes as effective ways to teach the low-code approach. This approach would provide students with the opportunity to learn low-code, but the choice to participate would be optional.

In France, faculty members from both Computer Science and non-Computer Science disciplines exhibit a keen interest in receiving training in low-code capabilities, though their focal points and perceived benefits vary. Faculty

members also in both Greek focus groups expressed interest in receiving training on low-code capabilities and uses. Preferred training methods varied, with some participants favouring in-person workshops and seminars for hands-on experience and direct interaction with instructors. Others preferred online resources, including webinars, video tutorials, and interactive e-learning platforms for self-paced learning. A hybrid approach combining in-person and online training was also suggested, and participants emphasized the importance of tailored content to cater to faculty members from different disciplines. In Croatia, half of the focus group participants expressed interest in receiving training on the capabilities and uses of low-code. Those interested preferred examples of software developed using a low-code approach and solutions for specific business areas. Serbian participants in the focus group expressed a strong interest in receiving training on low-code capabilities and uses. They were open to various training formats, including live or online workshops, short-cycle programs, and the use of online platforms. They recognized the need for training tailored to their needs and research requirements. Austrian participants suggested the establishment of extra-curricular courses or integration into existing IT classes as effective training methods for the low-code development approach.

Regarding the interest in LightCode Project updates, Participants in France are interested in professional development opportunities, such as workshops and seminars that offer hands-on experience with low-code platforms. They consider these beneficial not just for improving their teaching methods but also for their own career advancement.

Most participants in both Greek focus groups expressed a strong interest in receiving updates on the educational materials and tools produced by the LightCode project. They saw value in these materials for enhancing their teaching methods and staying updated with the latest developments in low-code technology. Participants emphasized the importance of receiving regular updates and were willing to provide feedback or collaborate with the LightCode

project team. However, in Croatia, interest in receiving updates on the materials produced by the LightCode project was limited, with only three out of eight participants indicating interest. Others either made no comments or expressed no interest. Serbian participants in the focus group were highly interested in receiving updates on the teaching and learning materials produced by the LightCode project. They recognized the potential value of these materials for their teaching methods and staying up-to-date with low-code technology developments. Austria did not provide specific feedback regarding interest in LightCode project updates.

FACULTY MEMBERS' FINDINGS - CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The insights gathered from faculty members across the five partner countries — France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria — regarding the implementation of low-code application development in higher education reveal both opportunities and challenges. These findings provide valuable guidance for institutions, educators, and policymakers aiming to leverage low-code approaches to enhance teaching, research, and administrative processes.

Opportunities:

Enhanced Student Learning and Engagement: Faculty members across the partner countries recognize the potential of low-code application development to enrich the learning experience. Ideas such as interactive quizzes, virtual labs, collaborative study platforms, and language learning applications illustrate how low-code tools can make learning more engaging and effective. This presents an opportunity to align teaching methods with modern pedagogical strategies that prioritize active learning, problem-solving, and creativity.

Streamlined Administrative Processes: The application of low-code in higher education administrative tasks, such as course scheduling, academic management, and feedback collection, can lead to improved efficiency and resource allocation. These streamlined processes can free up staff to focus on more complex tasks and enhance the overall administrative experience for both students and faculty.

Support for Research Activities: Low-code development offers researchers tools for data collection, analysis, visualization, and collaboration. This can expedite research projects, especially in interdisciplinary endeavors that require rapid application development. Faculty members can leverage low-code

platforms to prototype and test research ideas, enhancing the quality and speed of research outcomes.

Cross-Disciplinary Collaboration: Low-code development can foster cross-disciplinary teaching and research collaborations. Faculty members envision partnering with colleagues from diverse academic backgrounds to create courses and projects that incorporate low-code application development. This approach enriches the educational experience and promotes holistic problem-solving.

Alignment with Industry Demands: Recognizing the practical skills gap in the job market, faculty members believe that teaching low-code in higher education equips students with valuable industry-relevant skills. This alignment with industry trends enhances graduates' employability and competitiveness.

Challenges:

Awareness and Familiarity: A few faculty members displayed limited awareness of terms such as "low-code" and "citizen developer". Bridging this awareness gap and providing clear definitions of key concepts is essential for effective implementation.

Varying Levels of Interest: While many faculty members expressed enthusiasm for low-code development, some were less interested or uncertain about its relevance to their disciplines. Recognizing and addressing diverse interests and concerns is crucial when designing training programs and educational materials.

Training Diversity: Faculty members have varying preferences for training methods, including in-person workshops, online resources, and hybrid approaches. Tailoring training programs to accommodate these diverse preferences is essential for successful adoption.

Quality and Relevance of Materials: Faculty members expect high-quality, up-to-date, and discipline-specific educational materials. Ensuring that the content meets these expectations is essential for effective training and adoption.

Conclusions

The focus groups provided valuable insights into the faculty members' perspectives on low-code development, revealing both shared views and differences stemming from their respective fields. These findings suggest a generally positive outlook on the role of low-code development in higher education, albeit with specific concerns that need to be addressed. The strong interest in low-code training across disciplines indicates a fertile ground for the integration of low-code approaches into academic curricula and professional development programs.

The divergent views on certain topics, such as the concept of "Citizen Developer," indicate areas where further dialogue and education might be beneficial. Overall, the insights gained from these focus groups offer a comprehensive understanding that could guide future educational policies, curriculum development, and training programs in the realm of low-code development.

Recommendations:

Awareness Campaigns: Institutions should prioritize awareness campaigns and training programs to introduce faculty members to low-code development concepts, terminologies, and their potential benefits. Clear and accessible educational materials should be made available.

Customized Training: Offer customized training programs that cater to faculty members from various disciplines and backgrounds. Provide flexibility in training formats, including in-person workshops, online resources, and hybrid options.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration: Encourage and facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration among faculty members. Create opportunities for cross-disciplinary course development and research projects that incorporate low-code development.

Quality Assurance: Maintain a focus on the quality and relevance of educational materials and training programs. Engage faculty members in the development process to ensure alignment with their specific needs.

Evaluation and Feedback: Implement mechanisms for continuous evaluation and feedback. Faculty members' input can inform adjustments to training programs and materials, ensuring ongoing improvement.

Employability Focus: Emphasize the employability benefits of low-code development skills to students. Highlight the relevance of these skills in the job market to motivate student participation in related courses.

Regular Updates: Ensure regular updates and communication regarding the progress of initiatives like the LightCode project. Faculty members value access to the latest developments in low-code technology and education.

In conclusion, the insights from faculty members across the partner countries highlight the potential of low-code application development in higher education. By addressing challenges and capitalizing on opportunities, institutions can harness the power of low-code to enhance teaching, research, and administrative processes while equipping students with valuable skills for the future job market.

STUDENTS' FINDINGS

1. Description of the participants

A total of 442 university students participated in the survey through questionnaires across the partner countries. The analysis of university students' questionnaires from France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria provides valuable insights into the demographics, educational backgrounds, and experiences of social exclusion among respondents, and reveals a diverse student population across partner countries.

More specifically, in France, among the 154 students, the vast majority fall within the age range of 18 to 25 years. Specifically, 148 students, or a striking 96.10%, are in this youthful age bracket. This is followed by a relatively smaller group of 5 students (3.25%) who are aged between 26 and 30 years. A lone individual (0.65%) reported being in the age range of 31 to 40 years, adding a touch of age diversity to the dataset. When it comes to the gender landscape among the participants, 98 students identified as female, making up 63.64% of the respondents. This is contrasted by 51 male students, who constitute 33.12% of the total. Additionally, 4 students (2.60%) chose the 'Other' category, while one student (0.65%) opted for not disclosing their gender. In terms of experience with social exclusion, 92 students (59.74%) have fortunately not faced exclusion due to factors like gender, ethnicity, or socioeconomic status. Conversely, 51 students (33.12%) have had such experiences, lending a serious note to the dataset. A group of 11 students (7.14%) choose to abstain from answering this query, adding a layer of complexity to the social landscape captured in this survey. Educationally, the majority of our respondents are currently engaged in undergraduate studies. A total of 101 students (65.58%) are at this academic stage. This is followed by 49 students (31.82%) who are pursuing a Master's degree. A smaller fraction, just 4 students (2.60%), reported being at the high school level. The academic departments or faculties represented in the responses are notably

diverse. While a detailed breakdown would be cumbersome due to this diversity, the most frequent responses include Dauphine University and PSL, each with multiple mentions. With this rich and varied pool of participants, the French dataset offers a multi-faceted glimpse into the current educational and social settings of university students.

The Greek student sample comprised 109 respondents, with 81% falling within the 18-30 age group. The gender distribution was almost evenly divided. While 60% of Greek respondents indicated that they had completed their undergraduate degree, there was a possibility of misunderstanding the question, considering the respondents' age. The majority of participants were from faculties related to economics, with fewer clear responses regarding their field of study. Approximately 14% of Greek students reported experiencing social exclusion in their lifetime, with reasons including factors like ethnicity, gender, socioeconomic status, body type, and physical impairment.

The Croatian student sample consisted of 89 respondents, with the majority (88.76%) falling within the 18-25 age group. The sample was predominantly male. Approximately two-thirds of respondents reported never experiencing exclusion in their lifetime. The Croatian sample included students from various study fields, with the Faculty of Economics & Business in the University of Zagreb being the most represented. The distribution of educational levels included those pursuing bachelor's, and master's education. Two-thirds of Croatian students reported never experiencing exclusion. Among those who did, gender-related exclusion and socioeconomic status were the most common reasons.

In Serbia, 51 students responded to the questionnaire. Most of them (76.5%) were aged 18-25, with 57% being male and 41% female. Nearly half of the respondents reported experiencing some form of social exclusion, primarily related to economic factors. In Serbia, 63% of participants appeared to have completed or were currently attending their bachelor's studies. The majority of

respondents were from the Faculty of Economics and the Faculty of Electronic Engineering. Close to half of Serbian students faced some form of barrier during their lifetime, primarily economic, followed by political, technological, and physical barriers.

In Austria, 39 students participated in the survey, with 66.7% falling within the 18-25 age group. The gender distribution was fairly balanced. About 43.6% of respondents reported having experienced exclusion, with reasons including gender, race, and others. Austrian respondents were pursuing various levels of education, with 46.2% studying for a bachelor's degree, 35.9% for a master's degree, and 2.6% at the Ph.D. level. The majority (52%) were enrolled in technical universities. About 43.6% of Austrian students reported experiences of exclusion, with reasons including gender, race, and others.

2. Familiarity with the low-code development approach

Regarding the familiarity with Low-Code, the French student population surveyed appears to be largely unfamiliar with the term. Specifically, 134 out of the 154 respondents, constituting a notable 87.01%, indicated that they had never heard of it. This leaves only 20 students (12.99%) who are acquainted with the term, thereby underscoring a significant gap in awareness. When asked what they think the term "low-code application development" includes, the answers varied. However, it's worth mentioning that 7 students stated outright that they didn't know, while others mentioned not having any idea, further emphasizing the lack of familiarity.

Over 50% of Greek students had never heard of the term "low-code application development". Only 17% reported receiving some form of training on low-code, primarily during their studies. Despite the low familiarity, many respondents could correctly guess the meaning of low-code, associating it with easier or broader programming approaches. In Croatia, more than 78% of students were

not familiar with the low-code approach. Their understanding of the term "low-code application development" was limited, indicating a low level of knowledge about low-code concepts. A large majority had not received any training on low-coding. Also, the majority of Serbian students (72.5%) were not familiar with the term "low-code application development". Those who had heard of it attempted to provide explanations, often describing it as a form of programming with less coding involvement. Only a small percentage had prior low-code training experience. Similarly, in Austria, a significant proportion (74.4%) of participants had never heard of low-code development. However, those who were aware of it generally associated low-code with simplified or less extensive coding. About 20.5% of respondents reported having received training on low-code approaches, with varied examples of training contexts provided.

With regard to training on the low-code development approach, an overwhelming number of 144 students (93.51%) have not received any form of training. This complements the initial observation regarding the lack of awareness, with only 10 students (6.49%) confirming that they have undergone some training. A limited percentage (17%) of Greek students reported receiving training on low-code, primarily during their studies. This suggests a potential gap in incorporating low-code education into university curricula. Croatian students generally also lacked training in low-code, with few mentioning training experiences, such as WordPress seminars or exposure to low-code platforms during high school. In Serbia, a small proportion had prior low-code training (2%), while the majority had not received any training. This indicates a need for targeted educational efforts in low-code. Interestingly, about 20.5% of Austrian students mentioned receiving training on low-code approaches, though the context varied. This highlights that some students have had exposure to low-code concepts.

When questioned if they think they've ever used a low-code environment without realizing it, the responses from French students were quite balanced.

A total of 78 students (50.65%) believe they have not, while 60 students (38.96%) think they have, suggesting that low-code environments might be more embedded in their activities than initially assumed. In terms of actual usage of specific low-code environments, the answers were diverse, ranging from WordPress to Google Apps. Approximately 40% of Greek students believed they had used low-code environments without realizing it. In the following question, many students mentioned using Google Apps, WordPress, and similar environments, suggesting potential exposure to low-code tools. Over 48% of Croatian students believed they had used a low-code platform without knowing it. Commonly mentioned low-code environments included Google Apps, WordPress, and PowerApps. More than 52% of Serbian students believed they had used low-code environments without realizing it. They mentioned various platforms such as WordPress, Google Apps, Bubble, Salesforce, and Joomla. The majority of Austrian students (30.8%) stated they had not used any of the listed low-code environments. Among those who had, Google Apps and WordPress were the most commonly cited examples

3. Advantages & Disadvantages of the low-code development approach

The analysis of university students' perceptions of low-code advantages and disadvantages across partner countries provides insights into how the younger generation views this emerging technology. More specifically, France students consider "Security risks" as the most crucial advantage, with an average rating of 3.29. This is closely followed by the benefit of "Higher productivity across teams", which scored an average rating of 3.26. The third most important advantage, according to the students, is the "Lower barrier to entry, deployment cost and time", with an average rating of 3.20. It is evident that students value the security and efficiency that low-code environments can offer, as well as the accessibility and affordability of these platforms.

Greek students rated several advantages of low-code highly, with the top-rated ones being "lower barrier to entry, deployment cost, and time", "decreased costs", and "rapid assembly of solutions by a non-technical audience". They gave these advantages an average score of 4.0 or higher. This suggests that students appreciate the accessibility and cost-effectiveness of low-code development. However, they considered "effective risk management and governance" and "democratization of software development" to be less important.

Croatian students, unlike faculty members, placed a high value on certain advantages of low-code. They rated "faster transformation", "lower barrier to entry", and "better customer experience" as the most important advantages. This indicates that they recognize the potential for low-code to drive innovation and improve user satisfaction.

Serbian students considered "decreased costs", "higher productivity across teams", and "easily changeable solutions" as the most important advantages of low-code. This aligns with the broader benefits of cost-efficiency and flexibility associated with low-code. They gave these advantages high ratings, suggesting a positive perception of low-code's impact on productivity and cost-effectiveness.

Austrian students identified "lower barrier to entry" and "rapid assembly of solutions by a non-technical audience" as the most significant advantages of low-code, indicating their appreciation for the technology's accessibility and ease of use. They also recognized the importance of "improved agility" and "better customer experience".

Regarding the disadvantages, in France, "security risks" stood out as the most significant disadvantage, with an average rating of 3.29. This is an interesting finding, as it suggests that students see security as both an advantage and a concern, depending on the context. The next two most notable disadvantages were "Can't be applied to more complex processes" and "Low-code

development platforms have limitations", with average ratings of 2.72 and 2.57, respectively.

Greek students also rated "security risks" as the most important disadvantage of low-code, suggesting concerns about the potential vulnerabilities associated with this approach. They also considered "the need for a basic understanding of the programming world" as a disadvantage. However, it's worth noting that students gave lower average ratings to the disadvantages compared to the advantages.

Croatian students placed significant weight on "security risks", "limitations", and "impossibility of application to more complex processes" as the main disadvantages of low-code. This indicates their awareness of potential challenges and limitations of low-code development.

Serbian students rated "security risks" and the "inapplicability to more complex processes" as the most important disadvantages of low-code. They also considered the "lack of a unique interface" and "no ownership of the source code" as disadvantages. Despite these concerns, the average rating for disadvantages was lower than that for advantages, suggesting a relatively balanced view.

Again, Austrian students identified "security risks" and "no ownership of the source code" as the most significant disadvantages of low-code. They also recognized that low-code might have limitations in handling complex processes. Interestingly, they considered "a basic understanding of the programming world" as less important, indicating that they may see low-code as accessible to those with limited coding knowledge.

4. The low-code development approach & Higher Education

The analysis of university students' perceptions of low-code usage and expectations provides nuanced insights into their familiarity with the technology, their prior experiences, and their views on its potential. In France, 53.90% of the participants indicated that they have not used low-code application development approaches in their career so far. This is followed by 37 students (24.03%) who have used it and 34 students (22.08%) who are unsure, shedding light on a somewhat cautious or unexplored stance towards low-code in their professional journey.

In Greece, only 17% of the surveyed students stated that they have used low-code application development approaches. A substantial majority (over 70%) of respondents either had never heard of low-code or had not received any training on it. This suggests that low-code is not yet widely integrated into the academic curriculum or the early career development of Greek students.

The situation in Croatia mirrors that of Greece, with 58.4% of respondents reporting that they have never used low-code applications in their careers. Similar to their Greek counterparts, many Croatian students cited a lack of awareness and training as significant barriers to using low-code effectively.

Serbian students also reflected the same trend, with only 12% reporting prior low-code usage. The majority of respondents faced difficulties in using low-code, primarily due to a lack of knowledge or training. However, their responses indicated a clear interest in exploring the technology's potential benefits.

Austrian students exhibited limited exposure to low-code, with 64.1% reporting no previous usage. Despite this, these students expressed a wide range of expectations and potential benefits associated with low-code usage. Their diverse responses indicated a willingness to explore and experiment with this technology.

Across the partner countries, students' expectations and perceived benefits of low-code were closely aligned with the technology's core advantages:

- **Ease and Speed:** Students frequently associated low-code with ease, speed, and flexibility in application development. They perceived it as an opportunity to quickly turn their ideas into reality and develop practical skills that could benefit them academically and professionally.
- **Accessibility:** Students recognized low-code's potential to make application development more accessible to individuals with limited coding knowledge. They viewed it as a means to democratize software development, enabling more people to participate in creating digital solutions.
- **Innovation:** Students believed that integrating low-code learning into higher education could stimulate innovation and creativity. They saw it as a tool that could generate new ideas and solutions, particularly in non-technical fields.
- **Learning and Skill Development:** Many students viewed low-code as a valuable educational tool, allowing them to gain hands-on experience and acquire skills relevant to today's job market. They perceived it as a practical bridge between theoretical knowledge and practical application in their studies.
- **Efficiency:** Students recognized low-code's potential to streamline processes and reduce development time, making it an efficient approach for prototyping and problem-solving.

While students expressed interest and optimism about low-code, they also acknowledged potential challenges, such as security risks and limitations in handling complex processes. However, their overall positive attitude suggests a genuine willingness to explore and embrace low-code as a valuable addition to their educational and professional journeys.

5. Familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer"

The analysis of university students' familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer" highlights the limited awareness of this concept among the surveyed students across the partner countries. In France, the term "Citizen Developer" appears to be largely unfamiliar among the student population surveyed. A significant 144 out of 154 students (93.51%) indicated they had never heard of the term before. Only a small fraction, 7 students (4.55%), said they were familiar with it, while 3 students (1.95%) were unsure. Given the low levels of familiarity, it's not surprising that there's a broad range of interpretations about what the term "Citizen Developer" could mean. A total of 145 unique responses were recorded, indicating a variety of perspectives.

In Greece, students exhibited a particularly low level of familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer". Less than 10% of the respondents had heard the term before, indicating a lack of exposure to this concept. Furthermore, when asked to explain the term, nearly half of the students provided no answer. Among those who did respond, only a few demonstrated some degree of understanding.

Croatian students also displayed a significant lack of familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer," with 82% reporting that they had never heard of it. When asked to provide an explanation, their responses generally indicated a rudimentary understanding, describing a "person with no or basic knowledge in coding who can create an output based on code".

Similar to their Greek and Croatian participants, Serbian students had limited knowledge of the term "Citizen Developer." Over 72% of the respondents had not encountered this term before. Among those who had, approximately 18% claimed to understand its meaning to some extent. However, their responses varied widely, reflecting a diverse range of interpretations, from someone who develops apps without formal training to end-users being involved in application development.

Austrian students, too, exhibited a high degree of unfamiliarity with the term "Citizen Developer," with 82.1% reporting that they had never heard of it. When asked to explain the term, their responses were varied and occasionally vague, with some students associating it with individuals who lack formal coding training but can still develop applications. Others expressed uncertainty or provided unrelated interpretations.

6. Low-code approach & the business world

The analysis of students' perspectives on the application of low-code in the real world, specifically in the business context, reveals several insights regarding their beliefs about low-code adoption, the potential for citizen developers, and their perceptions of benefits for businesses. In France, a considerable number of students, the 54.55%, believe that low-code approaches are used in the business world. This is contrasted by 38 students (24.68%) who think otherwise and 32 students (20.78%) who are unsure. In Greece, approximately 75% of the students surveyed believe that businesses either use or might use low-code approaches. This finding demonstrates a level of optimism among students about the relevance and potential adoption of low-code development in the business world. Croatian students exhibit a similar belief, with a majority thinking that the business community utilizes or may utilize low-code. This suggests that students in Croatia also perceive low-code as a relevant technology in the business world. In Serbia, more than 78% of the students believe that businesses use or might use low-code approaches, indicating a high level of awareness and acceptance of this technology's relevance to the business sector. Austrian students expressed somewhat lower confidence, with 59% believing that low-code approaches are used in the business world. Although this percentage is slightly lower than in other partner countries, it still demonstrates a significant portion of students acknowledging the presence of low-code in the business landscape.

The sentiment towards the growing need for Citizen Developers is optimistic in France, with the 63.64% of the participants affirming the trend. Over 80% of Greek students believe that there is or might be an increased need for citizen developers. This suggests that they recognize the potential for individuals without extensive coding backgrounds to play a significant role in application development. Similar to their Greek counterparts, Croatian students also have a high belief in the need for citizen developers, highlighting their awareness of the growing demand for individuals who can create applications with limited coding expertise. Serbian students strongly concur, with more than 74% believing in an increased need for citizen developers. This aligns with the global trend of businesses seeking individuals who can leverage low-code platforms to develop solutions without deep programming knowledge. Austrian students, however, appear to have some doubts about the need for citizen developers, with 48.7% expressing uncertainty. Nevertheless, a significant portion remains open to the idea of increased demand for citizen developers.

Students across the partner countries identified several benefits for businesses resulting from the practical application of low-code development approaches in the real world. These benefits include:

- **Easier Implementation:** Many students highlighted that low-code makes implementation easier, reducing the complexity of developing software solutions.
- **Cost Savings:** Students emphasized the potential for businesses to save costs through low-code development, as it eliminates the need for specialized employees in coding and reduces the resources required.
- **Flexibility:** Low-code offers flexibility, enabling businesses to adapt to changing needs and requirements more easily.
- **Speed:** The speed of application development was a recurring theme, with students acknowledging that low-code can accelerate the development process.

- **Accessibility:** Low-code platforms allow more team members, even those without advanced coding skills, to participate in application development projects.
- **Efficiency:** Students recognized that low-code can lead to more efficient and effective solutions, streamlining business processes.

While many students expressed beliefs in the benefits of low-code, relatively few provided concrete ideas for applications that could be developed using low-code approaches. The most common ideas mentioned include the creation of websites or e-commerce platforms. Some students also proposed applications related to organizational tasks, such as financial management and client list management.

7. Training on Low-code approach

The students' responses regarding their interest in receiving training on the possibilities and use of low-code were generally positive across the surveyed countries. In France, a large proportion of students, 101 out of 154 (65.58%), responded positively. Students seem to prefer online formats, mentioning "Courses online" and "MOOC" (Massive Open Online Courses). This suggests an eagerness to learn more about the subject. In the same direction, a notable 65% of Greek students expressed their interest in receiving low-code training. They indicated various preferences for the training format, with a preference for online courses, seminars, or platform-based learning. Some students also showed interest in having low-code courses available within their faculty. Croatian respondents also demonstrated a strong interest in low-code training. They predominantly favoured online courses as their preferred mode of training. Additionally, some students provided their email addresses to stay updated on the outcomes of the LightCode project, indicating their eagerness to engage with low-code education and research. The interest in low-code training among Serbian students was mixed, with nearly equal numbers of

positive and negative responses. However, those interested in training expressed a desire for live or online training through platforms, seminars, video tutorials, and short courses at the faculty. Some students saw the potential value in learning about low-code for future use and research opportunities, while others held more critical views. In Austria, 41% of students expressed interest in low-code training. They suggested various ways to deliver the training, including face-to-face courses, online courses for specific projects, through their university, or via tutorials and lectures. Students also emphasized the importance of understanding the versatility of low-code and its potential application in their respective fields.

STUDENTS' FINDINGS - CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

Low-code development is emerging as a transformative force in software development, enabling rapid application creation with minimal coding expertise. Understanding the perceptions and attitudes of university students across different countries toward low-code is crucial, as these students will shape the future of software development. This analysis draws upon the results of students' questionnaires from five partner countries, including France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria, to provide general conclusions and recommendations for the adoption of low-code development in higher education.

Thus, the most important conclusions are the following:

Positive Student Perceptions: Students across the partner countries generally hold positive perceptions of low-code development. They recognize the advantages of reduced costs, increased speed, ease of use, and flexibility associated with low-code. This positivity suggests that low-code has the potential to gain traction in academia and the business world as these students enter the workforce.

Varied Levels of Familiarity: The students' familiarity with low-code and related concepts, such as "citizen developer," varied widely. While some students had prior knowledge and experience with low-code, a significant portion had limited or no exposure. This disparity highlights the need for comprehensive educational programs that cater to students with diverse levels of expertise.

Awareness of Real-World Application: Students displayed a growing awareness of the practical applications of low-code in the business world. They believed that businesses could benefit from low-code approaches and

recognized the potential need for citizen developers, who can bridge the gap between business needs and technical solutions.

Diverse Ideas for Low-Code Applications: While not all students provided specific ideas for low-code applications, some demonstrated creativity by proposing low-code solutions across various domains, including web development, organization, healthcare, and education. This suggests that students perceive low-code as a versatile tool with wide-ranging potential.

Interest in Training: A substantial number of students expressed a strong interest in receiving training on the possibilities and use of low-code. They predominantly favoured online courses, seminars, and platform-based learning. This eagerness to learn signifies an opportunity to integrate low-code education into higher education curricula.

Taking all the aforementioned into account, the following recommendations can be made:

Incorporate Low-Code Education: Universities and educational institutions should consider incorporating low-code development education into their curricula. This should cater to students with varying levels of prior knowledge, offering introductory and advanced courses.

Online Training Resources: Given the preference for online training, universities should provide access to comprehensive online resources, including courses, tutorials, and seminars. Collaborations with low-code platforms and providers can facilitate access to these resources.

Multidisciplinary Approach: Encourage a multidisciplinary approach to low-code education, emphasizing its applicability across various fields, including business, healthcare, and education. This approach can broaden students' perspectives and foster innovation.

Faculty Training: Train faculty members to effectively teach low-code development. Faculty development programs can ensure that educators are well-equipped to deliver high-quality low-code education.

Research Opportunities: Promote research initiatives related to low-code development. Encourage students, particularly those pursuing advanced degrees, to explore low-code's potential in solving real-world problems.

Industry Collaboration: Foster collaboration between educational institutions and industry partners. Industry experts can provide valuable insights, guest lectures, and internship opportunities, enhancing students' practical knowledge.

Engage Student Communities: Create low-code development communities and student groups to facilitate peer learning and knowledge sharing. Such communities can organize hackathons, workshops, and projects that apply low-code solutions to real challenges.

Continuous Assessment: Continuously assess the effectiveness of low-code education through feedback mechanisms and surveys. Adapt curricula and resources based on student experiences and evolving industry trends.

The findings from students' questionnaires in the partner countries highlight a promising future for low-code development in higher education. Students' positive perceptions, growing awareness of real-world applications, and interest in training underscore the need for educational institutions to embrace low-code as an essential skillset. By implementing these recommendations, universities can empower students to leverage low-code for innovation, problem-solving, and addressing the evolving needs of the digital world. This proactive approach will not only benefit students but also contribute to the broader adoption of low-code in the professional sphere.

STAKEHOLDERS' FINDINGS

1. Description of the participants

A total of 75 stakeholders participated in the survey through questionnaires across the partner countries – France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria, aiming to capture the perspectives and characteristics of individuals and organizations interested in or benefiting from low-code development.

In a survey conducted across France, 20 diverse stakeholders from businesses, public organizations, NGOs, and freelancers were consulted to gauge the impact and relevance of low-code technologies. The participants represented a broad age spectrum, with 40% aged 51 or more, 30% between 26-30 years, 20% between 41-50 years, and 10% between 31-40 years, ensuring a range of perspectives. Gender distribution was balanced with 50% male, 45% female, and 5% undisclosed. Regarding social exclusion, 70% reported no experience of it, while 15% did and another 15% chose not to disclose. Most respondents (75%) held a Master's degree, with others having a Ph.D., other qualifications, or pursuing undergraduate studies. The participants were predominantly from private (45%) and public (35%) organizations, with 20% being freelancers. They worked in varied fields like consulting, training, software engineering, and education. Half of the respondents did not focus on social inclusion, while 35% did, and 15% were unsure. Those focusing on social inclusion targeted diverse vulnerable groups such as underrepresented individuals in higher education, neurodivergent people, queer communities, and immigrants.

In Greece, 22 stakeholders responded to the questionnaire. The sample consisted of 13 men and 9 women of varying ages. Notably, 5 respondents reported experiencing social exclusion at some point in their lives due to factors like gender, age, or disability. Most of the participants held either bachelor's or master's degrees. Furthermore, the majority of stakeholders worked in private companies or organizations, and eight of them had roles related to the

social inclusion of vulnerable groups, which is of particular interest. The Greek stakeholders' questionnaire captured a diverse group with notable representation from individuals involved in social inclusion efforts. The presence of respondents who experienced social exclusion underscores the importance of inclusive initiatives like low-code development.

The Croatian sample comprised 11 participants from various business sectors, such as R&D, IT, finance, data science, media, and consultancy. The respondents were primarily in the 31-40 age group, and 54.55% were males. A significant portion of the sample, almost two-thirds, had never experienced exclusion in their lifetime. Most respondents held master's degrees, and the majority worked in private companies. None of the respondents were engaged in activities aimed at the social inclusion of vulnerable groups. In Croatia, the stakeholders' sample primarily comprised practitioners in various sectors. While none of the respondents were directly engaged in social inclusion efforts, their diverse backgrounds provide valuable insights into the potential impact of low-code adoption.

In Serbia, 11 stakeholders participated in the survey, consisting of 9 men and 2 women. The respondents represented different age groups, with a significant portion falling within the 41-50 age bracket. Four participants reported experiencing social exclusion at some point in their lives, citing reasons related to gender, age, or disability. Most of the stakeholders held master's degrees, and they primarily worked in private companies or organizations. Two participants had roles related to the social inclusion of vulnerable groups. The Serbian stakeholders' questionnaire revealed that some respondents had experienced social exclusion. This context underscores the relevance of low-code solutions that can empower diverse groups and reduce barriers to participation.

Austria's survey involved 11 stakeholders, with 54.5% being male and 45.5% female. The majority of respondents were in the 41-50 age group.

Approximately 27.7% of participants had experienced exclusion during their lives, with gender-related factors being a common cause. Most respondents worked in private companies or organizations, with diverse roles ranging from marketing and management to engineering and consulting. Only 27.3% of the participants' work aimed at the social inclusion of vulnerable groups, such as people with disabilities and women. Austria's stakeholders' questionnaire highlighted that gender-related exclusion experiences were present among respondents. Despite limited involvement in social inclusion activities, the diverse professional backgrounds of respondents suggest varied perspectives on low-code adoption.

2. Familiarity with the low-code development approach

Regarding stakeholders' knowledge and familiarity with low-code, in France, 60% of the participants indicated that they have heard of the term. The survey also aimed to gauge what respondents think low-code development encompasses. The answers were varied, each representing about 5% of the total. Responses ranged from "few lines of code and technical knowledge to build apps" to "ability to develop applications without coding" and "applications made for users with little knowledge of coding". When asked about receiving training in low-code approaches, the majority, 80%, indicated that they have not received any form of training in this area. Only the 20% of participants mentioned having received training. Among those, one respondent noted they went through classes at their college involving Blender and Grasshopper, and another mentioned that managing a low-code platform was part of their training. Interestingly, a considerable number of respondents, 70%, believe they have used a low-code environment without realizing it. WordPress was the most commonly cited platform.

In Greece, around 50% of stakeholders had heard of the term "low-code." However, only 3 out of 22 respondents reported receiving some form of training

on low-code. Encouragingly, almost all stakeholders provided responses explaining what "developing applications via low-code" could entail. Moreover, approximately half of them believed they had used low-code environments at some point, with WordPress and Google Apps being the most commonly mentioned platforms.

Croatian stakeholders displayed a better prior knowledge of low-code compared to students and faculty members, with 45.45% having heard of the term. Many stakeholders provided detailed responses elaborating on the low-code concept. However, the majority had not received any formal training on low-code. Nonetheless, a significant portion believed they had used low-code platforms without realizing it, with WordPress and Google Apps being the most frequently mentioned examples.

In Serbia, over 55% of stakeholders had heard of the term low-code and were familiar with it, although only 1 out of 11 respondents had received some training in it through an IT bootcamp. Stakeholders provided insightful explanations of "low-code application development," highlighting its potential for rapid MVP development and simplifying software development. Notably, only 2 respondents believed they had used low-code environments without realizing it, indicating a higher level of awareness regarding low-code. Commonly mentioned low-code platforms included WordPress, Google Apps, Joomla, Salesforce, and Bubble.

Austrian stakeholders had relatively less prior knowledge of low-code, with 72.7% having never heard of the term. Despite this, many stakeholders intuitively grasped its meaning, describing it as an easy way to use digital techniques for problem-solving and a means for non-technical individuals to create applications and websites. A majority of respondents had not received any training on low-code, and only a few mentioned attending workshops related to specific low-code environments. Interestingly, 45.5% believed they

had used low-code environments without realizing it, citing platforms like WordPress, Google Apps, Joomla, Salesforce, and Bubble.

3. Advantages & Disadvantages of the low-code development approach

Across the partner countries, stakeholders highlighted several key advantages of low-code development. These advantages have significant implications for businesses and organizations, demonstrating the potential for low-code to address various needs and challenges:

- **Lower Barrier to Entry and Deployment Cost and Time:** Stakeholders consistently rated this as one of the most important advantages of low-code (France: 4.47/5, Greece: 4.2, Croatia: 4.2, Serbia: 4.09, Austria: 54.5% consider it very important). The ability to quickly develop applications without extensive coding knowledge reduces entry barriers and expedites deployment, potentially saving time and costs.
- **Improved Agility:** Respondents across countries recognized improved agility (France: 4.58/5, Greece: 4.2, Croatia: 3.9, Serbia: 3.91) as a valuable benefit of low-code. The flexibility and rapid development capabilities allow organizations to adapt to changing circumstances and market demands swiftly.
- **Higher Productivity Across Teams:** Austrian participants (54.5%) emphasized the importance of higher productivity across teams facilitated by low-code solutions. This underscores the potential for streamlining collaboration and accelerating project delivery.
- **Better Customer Experience:** Stakeholders in Greece (3.3/5), Croatia (3.11), and Austria (36.6%) recognized the potential for low-code to enhance customer experiences. By enabling the creation of user-friendly applications, organizations can offer improved services to their clients.

- **Democratization of Software Development:** In Austria, this was considered an important advantage by most participants (45.5%). Low-code democratizes software development by allowing non-technical individuals to participate in application creation, potentially expanding the pool of contributors.

While stakeholders identified numerous advantages, they also raised concerns about potential disadvantages associated with low-code development:

- **Security Risks:** Security was a significant concern across all countries (France: 4.45/5, Greece: 4.1, Croatia: 3.89, Serbia: 4.2, Austria: Most important). The perceived security risks associated with low-code platforms warrant careful consideration and mitigation strategies.
- **Limitations of Low-Code Platforms:** Respondents in Greece (4.1/5), Croatia (4), and Serbia (4) highlighted limitations as a major disadvantage. The inability to handle complex processes or implement specific features may restrict the applicability of low-code in certain scenarios.
- **Source Code Ownership:** While not rated as highly, source code ownership was still seen as a notable disadvantage (Greece: 3.3/5, Serbia: 2.78, Austria: Not important). Stakeholders raised concerns about their control over the source code when using low-code platforms.
- **Requirement of Programming Knowledge:** In Serbia (2.89) and Austria (Not important), some stakeholders mentioned the need for a basic understanding of programming as a disadvantage. This requirement could limit the accessibility of low-code to non-technical individuals.
- **Unique Interface:** In Austria (Not important), respondents did not see a unique interface as a significant disadvantage, while in Serbia (2.78), it was mentioned. This aspect concerns the distinctiveness of interfaces created using low-code.
- **Skipping Checks and Balances:** Some stakeholders expressed uncertainty about the importance of skipping checks and balances during production,

difficulty in implementing complex features by new developers, and the inability to apply low-code to more complex processes.

Consequently, stakeholders across partner countries generally recognized the potential benefits of low-code development, particularly its ability to lower entry barriers, reduce costs, and enhance agility. These advantages align with the broader goal of simplifying and accelerating the software development process.

However, stakeholders also voiced concerns about security risks, platform limitations, and the ownership of source code. These concerns emphasize the need for careful planning, risk mitigation, and selecting the appropriate use cases for low-code development.

The slightly higher average rating of disadvantages compared to advantages (Greece: 3.8/5 vs. 3.7/5) suggests a degree of skepticism regarding the full applicability of low-code in the business world. Stakeholders may be cautious about embracing low-code platforms without addressing potential risks adequately.

To successfully implement low-code solutions, organizations should consider these advantages and disadvantages in their decision-making processes, develop clear strategies for managing potential challenges, and explore opportunities for leveraging low-code development to its fullest potential.

4. The low-code development approach in practice

The awareness and usage of low-code among stakeholders in the partner countries vary. While stakeholders show a higher percentage of having used low-code compared to students, there is still a significant portion that either has never heard of the term or has not received relevant training.

In France, 45% confirmed they have used low-code approaches in their career, while all the others have not. Over 35% of stakeholders in Greece have used low-code at some point in their careers, demonstrating a higher adoption rate compared to students. However, more than half of the respondents either have never heard of the term or have not received relevant training. A large majority of respondents (90.1%) in Croatia have never used low-code applications in their careers, indicating limited exposure to this development approach among faculty members. In Serbia, approximately 36% of stakeholders have used low-code at some point in their careers. However, a significant portion (55%) has not, indicating potential untapped opportunities for low-code adoption. Many respondents mentioned they have never heard of low-code or have not received training. While in Austria, 27.3% of the participants have used low-code application development in their careers, while the same percentage has not. Additionally, 45.5% have no idea whether they have used it or not.

Stakeholders across the partner countries shared their expectations regarding what low-code application development could offer them. Their responses primarily revolved around practical advantages, highlighting the potential benefits of adopting low-code. More specifically, the responses from the French stakeholders ranged from "saving time" and "quick prototyping" to "more flexibility & productivity". Greek stakeholders emphasized the speed at which certain tasks could be performed and the reduced costs associated with low-code development. They also noted that highly skilled programming staff might not be required. Respondents in Croatia focused on speed and simplicity as the main advantages they expect from low-code. This aligns with the broader theme of efficiency and ease of use associated with low-code. Stakeholders in Serbia expected practical benefits, such as faster earnings, reduced coding work, and speedier processes. They also highlighted the potential for cost reduction and greater accessibility, even for those with limited coding knowledge. Participants in Austria mentioned various advantages, including faster deployment, lower training costs, increased structure, and a more

straightforward approach to work. Speed, simplicity, and the ability to find new solutions for daily activities were also emphasized.

Stakeholders generally have varying levels of awareness and experience with low-code application development. While some have used low-code and recognize its potential benefits, others have limited knowledge or have not received relevant training. This suggests an opportunity for expanding awareness and training programs, particularly among faculty members and business professionals.

The perceived benefits of low-code align with the overall advantages highlighted by students and faculty members, including speed, simplicity, cost reduction, and increased efficiency. These expectations underscore the practical advantages that low-code development can offer to a wide range of stakeholders.

5. Familiarity with the term "Citizen Developer"

The awareness and understanding of the term "Citizen Developer" among stakeholders in the partner countries is quite limited. Only a small percentage of respondents are familiar with the term, and those who are tend to have a relatively accurate understanding of it.

In France, a little over one-third of the participants, the 35% indicated that they have heard of the term. The majority, however, the 65% of the respondents, were not familiar with it. Definitions ranged from "someone who is a developer without having studied the field" to "a person who is not natively a Software Developer but can use software to achieve automation". In Greece, out of the 22 respondents, only one was familiar with the term "Citizen Developer". Furthermore, when asked to explain what they thought the term meant, responses were sparse, and only a few provided a relatively accurate description. Respondents in Croatia are mostly unfamiliar with the term "Citizen

Developer". When asked to explain the term, their responses generally revolved around the idea of individuals who are not trained in software development but are capable of using no- or low-code solutions to create useful apps. In Serbia, only 3 out of 11 respondents were familiar with the term "Citizen Developer", while the majority had not heard of it. However, among those who attempted to explain the term, the descriptions provided were relatively accurate, emphasizing accessibility and the ability of non-professionals to develop applications using low-code or no-code platforms. In Austria, the awareness of the term "Citizen Developer" is very low, with 90.9% of participants having never heard of it. Some participants shared their interpretations of the term, which generally conveyed the idea of non-professionals being able to develop applications.

Thus, the term "Citizen Developer" remains largely unfamiliar to stakeholders across the partner countries. Only a small percentage of respondents are acquainted with the term, and even among them, there is some variability in the understanding of what it means. This lack of awareness underscores the need for educational efforts to introduce and explain the concept of Citizen Developers. As this role becomes increasingly relevant in the context of low-code development, it is crucial for stakeholders to understand the potential of individuals outside of traditional IT roles being able to create software applications using user-friendly development platforms.

6. Low-code approach & the business world

Across the partner countries, stakeholders exhibit a varied level of adoption and perception of low-code approaches in their business or organizations, as well as in the broader business world. In France, 40% indicated that their organization does not use low-code, while 35% confirmed their company's engagement with low-code technologies. The remaining 25% were unsure, responding with "I don't know", which suggests a lack of awareness or

communication within some organizations about their technological strategies. When asked if they think the business world is utilizing low-code approaches, a majority of respondents, totalling 60%, believe it is possible, responding with "Maybe." Another 35% were more certain, answering "Yes", while only one respondent, or 5%, was unsure. In terms of the growing need for Citizen Developers, the majority view was optimistic. A total of 60% of respondents believe there is a growing need, while 35% consider it a possibility, responding with "Maybe". The perceived benefits of low-code approaches for businesses were diverse, capturing a myriad of perspectives. Respondents highlighted advantages such as "Faster time to market", "Cost savings", "Reducing repetitive tasks" and "Facilitating quick application creation by users".

In Greece, only a minority of stakeholders (about 18%) reported using low-code approaches in their businesses or organizations. However, a vast majority (86%) believes that the business world currently uses or may use low-code approaches in the future. A similar percentage (86%) also perceives a growing need for citizen developers. Stakeholders highlight the benefits of low-code in terms of speed, flexibility, and cost reduction. Notably, one respondent expressed concern about potential compromises in quality due to rapid development.

In Croatia, a smaller percentage of stakeholders (about 9.1%) reported using low-code in their companies. However, there is a notable belief that the business world is using or may adopt low-code approaches (81.8%). Nearly half (45.5%) see a growing need for citizen developers. Stakeholders emphasized the benefits of low-code in terms of agility, speed, and flexibility. Some respondents also provided specific ideas for applications that could be developed using low-code.

The usage of low-code approaches among Serbian stakeholders is relatively low, with only 27% indicating that they use it in their business or organization. However, a substantial portion (82%) believes that the business world uses or

may use low-code approaches, and 45% perceive an increasing need for citizen developers. The benefits cited by stakeholders include speed, flexibility, and cost reduction. It is worth noting that while many stakeholders mentioned these benefits, some did not respond to the question about ideas for low-code applications or were unwilling to share their ideas.

In Austria, a relatively higher percentage of participants (27.3%) reported using low-code approaches in their careers. A majority (72.7%) believes that the business world uses low-code approaches. The benefits associated with low-code, as highlighted by respondents, include cost reduction, increased availability of applications, and democratization of IT knowledge. Some participants also shared ideas for applications they could develop using low-code, such as CRM systems, data generation, or applications to improve team collaboration.

These findings suggest that there is a growing interest in low-code approaches among stakeholders, and as awareness and education continue to spread, the adoption of these approaches may increase in various industries and regions. This trend emphasizes the importance of providing training and resources to empower individuals to harness the potential of low-code development.

7. Training on Low-code approach

Stakeholders have varying levels of interest in receiving training on the capabilities and uses of low-code across the partner countries. In France, the majority of respondents were positive, with 13 individuals or 65% expressing interest. Conversely, a minority of 3 respondents, or 15%, were not interested in training. Interestingly, 4 participants, accounting for 20%, were undecided, indicating "I don't know". As for the preferred mode and objectives of the training, the responses were incredibly diverse. Some of the noted preferences included "Online training", "In person or remote" and specialized sessions.

In Greece, despite participating in the survey, most stakeholders do not express a desire to receive training on low-code (65%). Several factors could contribute to this, including scepticism about the utility of low-code or the perception that they lack the time to undergo training. Some stakeholders may prefer to hire individuals with expertise in low-code rather than investing in training themselves. For those interested in training, the preference is for online training, possibly due to time constraints.

The responses from Croatian stakeholders show a higher level of interest in receiving low-code training. A significant percentage of respondents express a preference for online courses as their preferred training platform. Additionally, some stakeholders are interested in receiving updates on the results produced within the LightCode project. This higher level of interest in training may indicate a willingness to explore the potential benefits of low-code.

Similar to Greece, a majority of Serbian stakeholders do not wish to receive training on low-code (64%). Reasons for this may include scepticism about low-code or time constraints. Some respondents even express an interest in providing training to others. Those interested in training prefer online methods, possibly due to convenience. Additionally, about half of the participating stakeholders express interest in receiving materials and newsletters created within the LightCode project, indicating a higher level of commitment.

In Austria, just over half of the participants (54.5%) express interest in receiving training on the capabilities and uses of low-code. They suggest various means of training, including online courses, training videos, project management, and case studies.

Therefore, stakeholders' interest in low-code training varies across countries, with some regions showing a higher level of interest than others. The lack of interest in training among stakeholders may be attributed to factors such as skepticism about the utility of low-code, time constraints, or a preference for hiring experts rather than undergoing training themselves.

However, online training methods are preferred by many stakeholders, possibly due to their convenience and flexibility, while some stakeholders express a willingness to receive updates on the results produced within the LightCode project, indicating ongoing interest and engagement in the project's outcomes.

These findings highlight the importance of tailoring training programs to meet the specific needs and preferences of stakeholders in each country. Additionally, efforts to address skepticism and communicate the benefits of low-code development may help increase interest and participation in training initiatives.

STAKEHOLDERS' FINDINGS - CONCLUSIONS & RECOMMENDATIONS

The stakeholders' questionnaires from the six partner countries — France, Greece, Croatia, Serbia, and Austria — have provided valuable insights into the perceptions, knowledge, and preferences related to low-code development. These findings offer a nuanced understanding of how various stakeholders view and engage with low-code technology in their respective contexts. The following key observations can be drawn from the collective responses:

Awareness and Knowledge Vary: Across the partner countries, there is a notable variation in the awareness and knowledge of low-code technology among stakeholders. While some respondents have a solid understanding of low-code and its applications, a significant proportion remain unfamiliar with the concept. This disparity suggests the need for targeted awareness campaigns and educational initiatives to bridge the knowledge gap.

Interest in Low-Code: Stakeholders' interest in low-code technology is influenced by their familiarity with it. Those who are more knowledgeable about low-code are generally more interested in its potential benefits. However, a considerable number of stakeholders, particularly in Greece and Serbia, exhibit skepticism or disinterest in low-code, which necessitates efforts to address misconceptions and communicate its advantages.

Benefits of Low-Code: Respondents across countries recognize the potential benefits of low-code, including lower entry barriers, decreased deployment costs and time, improved agility, and the democratization of software development. These advantages align with the principles of efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and accessibility.

Challenges and Concerns: Stakeholders also acknowledge the challenges and concerns associated with low-code, such as security risks, limitations in complex process handling, and potential quality issues. It is essential to

address these concerns through robust governance, security measures, and clear communication of low-code's scope and limitations.

Citizen Developers: The term "citizen developer" remains relatively unfamiliar to stakeholders, with only a few respondents correctly defining it. Educating stakeholders about the concept of citizen developers and their role in low-code development can help promote a more inclusive and accessible approach to application development.

Use of Low-Code: While a majority of stakeholders do not currently use low-code in their organizations, many believe that the business world, in general, utilizes or may benefit from low-code approaches. This indicates an awareness of the technology's potential impact and scalability.

Training and Education: Stakeholders' interest in low-code training varies, with some expressing a strong desire for training while others are less inclined. The preferred mode of training is online, possibly due to its flexibility and convenience. Addressing the reasons behind disinterest in training, such as skepticism or time constraints, is crucial to engage a wider audience.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the stakeholders' questionnaires, the following recommendations can guide the efforts of the LightCode project and its partners:

Awareness and Education Campaigns: Implement targeted awareness and education campaigns in each partner country to promote low-code technology. These campaigns should highlight the benefits, dispel misconceptions, and explain the role of citizen developers.

Customized Training Programs: Develop tailored training programs on low-code development to accommodate varying levels of knowledge and interest among stakeholders. Consider offering online training options to ensure accessibility.

Support Citizen Developers: Encourage the concept of citizen developers by providing resources and tools that empower non-technical individuals to participate in low-code development projects.

Address Concerns: Address stakeholders' concerns about security, quality, and limitations associated with low-code. Provide clear guidelines and best practices to mitigate these challenges.

Evaluate and Adapt: Continuously assess the effectiveness of awareness campaigns, training programs, and engagement efforts and adapt them based on feedback and evolving stakeholder needs

Engage Skeptics: Engage stakeholders who exhibit skepticism or disinterest in low-code by providing concrete examples of successful low-code implementations and their positive impact.

Encourage Collaboration: Promote collaboration between stakeholders, including businesses, public organizations, NGOs, and freelancers, to foster knowledge sharing and best practices in low-code development.

Regular Updates: Continue providing stakeholders with updates on the results and progress of the LightCode project to maintain their engagement and interest.

By implementing these recommendations, the LightCode project and its partners can work toward promoting the adoption of low-code technology, fostering a culture of innovation, and enhancing digital inclusion in the participating countries.